

1 **EHHADH functions in embryonic stem cell fate choice during endoderm lineage specification.**

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7 The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm,
8 mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or
9 important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We
10 describe a requirement for *EHHADH* in germ layer lineage choice from pluripotent stem cells in *Homo*
11 *sapiens*.

12 Citations

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1. Houten, S.M., Denis, S., Argmann, C.A., Jia, Y., Ferdinandusse, S., Reddy, J.K. and Wanders, R.J., 2012. Peroxisomal L-bifunctional enzyme (Ehhadh) is essential for the production of medium-chain dicarboxylic acids. *Journal of lipid research*, 53(7), pp.1296-1303.